

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief n° 4

How to consider impact when planning interventions to improve AMU

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This contributes to the objective of identifying levers/incentives for adherence to prudent use principles by veterinarians and farmers and of developing integrative strategies for animal health.

The European Union is the world's second largest pork producer and one of the world's largest poultry meat producers. EU is also a major producer of beef and veal with a total herd of around 78 million cattle and a substantial producer of milk and milk products with a total milk production around 155 million tonnes per year.

This policy brief should particularly relevant for policy-makers and stakeholders, as well as researchers and professionals interested in social innovation, from any European country.

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RELATED OUTPUTS

1. Guenin, M.-J., Studnitz, M., Molia, S. **Literature review of impact assessment applied to changes in antimicrobial use initiatives.** [Deliverable 6.1](#) ROADMAP project.
2. Guenin M-J, Belloc C, Ducrot C, de Romémont A, Peyre M, Molia S. A **participatory approach for building ex ante impact pathways towards a prudent use of antimicrobials in pig and poultry sectors in France.** [PLoS ONE. 2022, 17\(11\).](#)

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CONTEXT

Numerous interventions have been implemented over the last twenty years to decrease antimicrobial use in livestock, but there needs to be more information on the impacts generated by these interventions. Within the framework of the ROADMAP project, a scoping review was conducted to analyse which ones worked, how, for whom, and why. It showed that relationships between outputs (products of an intervention), outcomes (changes in practices, behaviour or interactions, and changes in knowledge, skills and motivation), impacts (long-term effects of the intervention) and contexts are complex. This scoping review showed no one-size-fits-all solution but semi-regularities among transition pathways and confirmed the need to use participatory strategic planning to design successful interventions.

Ex ante impact assessment aims to improve the construction of interventions by designing them strategically and conservatively and laying out the mechanisms through which impacts will be generated. It was used in the ROADMAP project in five countries where living labs were implemented to foster transitions towards prudent antimicrobial use. First, desired impacts were identified by living lab participants: they encompassed improvements in terms of antimicrobial use but also of animal health and welfare, economic resilience of farms and veterinary practices, collaboration among stakeholders and communication towards consumers. Then, extensive problem trees were built to identify i) which problems prevented the desired impacts from being reached, ii) among all these problems, which ones living lab participants felt able and legitimate to address. Finally, strategies were designed to solve the selected problems based on the specificities of the country context and the map of prominent, influential and impacted stakeholders. Impact pathways were built to specify which inputs would be used in each country to produce which outputs, which actors would do what differently by using these outputs, and how these outputs would contribute to the desired impacts.

FINDINGS FROM THE PROJECT

We need more information on the impacts of interventions to reduce antimicrobial use.

The theory of change is seldom explained when interventions are built, and their short to medium-term (outcomes) or long-term (impacts) effects are rarely quantified or evaluated.

Strategies that worked were tailored to the context

Past interventions that succeeded in improving antimicrobial use were based on various strategies, including: mandatory and not mandatory norms and standards, informative and educative measures, herd management support, economic support, etc.

Top-down strategies tended to be less successful than those involving stakeholders in their design.

Ex ante impact assessment can help

Ex ante impact assessment helps structure participatory processes and provides valuable outputs (problem trees, outcome maps, narratives) for building strategies.

Designing strategies based on impacts you want to achieve and transition pathways towards these impacts contributes to higher plausibility, acceptability and sustainability of interventions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Systematically document the theory of change of interventions aimed at improving antimicrobial use, and plan on calculating outcome and impact indicators.

Grey literature (e.g. returns of experience, ministry reports, etc.) should be translated into English and available online.

There is no magical solution or magical combination of solutions!

Participatory approaches take time, but they lead to interventions that are more likely to be successful because they consider the realities of animal farming and its larger context and engage stakeholders.

Context varies with time, and strategies need to be refined: e.g., motivation to improve antimicrobial use may fade when some threshold has been reached or when antimicrobial resistance becomes less important than other issues (health crisis, soaring energy prices, etc.).

When using ex-ante impact assessment to design strategies, think about the positive impacts you want to contribute to (e.g. decreased antimicrobial resistance or improved animal health and welfare) but also the adverse effects you want to avoid (e.g. decreased vet care access or decreased farm competitiveness).

Choose wisely the participants and facilitator for your ex-ante impact assessment process: a good variety of stakeholders helps build a systemic vision of problems, but tensions may arise when solutions to problems need to be chosen.

The ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 817626.

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